

Key Business Success of Inbound and Outbound Tourism Services Provider

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Strategy Management, Entrepreneurs' Skill, Green Environment Of Tourism And Business Success</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4990562</p>	<p><i>Successful businesses acquire a considerable benefit on investment and assets for the investors who invest their capital in the investment. Business success creates wealth for the investors and provides them future security. Hence, it is mandatory to take notice of effecting factors on business success. According to the current study, strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill significantly influence business success, especially in Thailand, with the mediation role of the green environment of tourism. Strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill have a direct influence on a green environment and business success. Six hundred twenty-two (622) entrepreneurs were surveyed to collect primary data to finalize the results of the current study. A statistical software Partial Least Square (PLS), was used to analyze the collected primary data for the accomplishment of end results. It is investigated that as good is a strategy management work, as will better be a business success. Moreover, skillful entrepreneurs acquire business success more regularly as compared with those who don't focus on their skills. Hence, practically, the current study provides a boost to grow business success for the entrepreneurs.</i></p>

Introduction

Business success is essential for every entrepreneur. However, there are several factors that directly and indirectly affect business success. Sometimes entrepreneurs successfully achieve their targets and gain considerable profits from their investment, and sometimes they fail. Multiple reasons are there due to which entrepreneurs have to face failure in business success. However, business success requires entrepreneurs' attention and capability to go through the whole business process (Amankwah-Amoah, Hinson, Honyenuga, & Lu, 2019). Generally, strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill have a meaningful influence on business success. Strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill are the factors that evaluate business success with their effectiveness, especially for Thailand's entrepreneurs.

The current study is about the role of strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill on business success with the mediating role of the green environment of tourism in Thailand. Hence, the entrepreneurs' business success incredibly involved in Thailand's tourism industry is necessary to be as substantial as it supports the country's green environment. The green environment of tourism sustains or maintains the economic, social, environmental, and cultural values of a region or country (Fernandes & Olivetti, 2020). Therefore, tourism's green environment has significant importance between the relationship of strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, and business success, particularly in Thailand.

However, entrepreneurs in Thailand are facing other business success related issues. The business success of Thai entrepreneurs is not sustainable. There are some reasons due to which business success of the entrepreneurs is not continual. Strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill are also one of the significant reasons which directly affects the business success of Thai entrepreneurs; however, green environment of tourism mediates between the relationship of strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, and business success. Hence, strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, and the green environment of tourism are responsible for business success (Kraus, Rehman, & García, 2020). According to the current study, the role of strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, and the green environment of tourism have a meaningful influence on business success, particularly in Thailand.

The current study investigating the role of strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, and green environment of tourism on business success in Thailand are unique in the body of literature. Different studies explored the role of strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill; however, these studies have missed exploring the relationship between strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, and business success. Research studies are also available on the mediation role of the green environment of tourism; however, the green environment of tourism for business success, particularly for the Thai entrepreneurs, is missing. Hence, the current study is a substantial contribution to the body of literature.

It is clear from the literature that strategy management leads to business success for entrepreneurs. Moreover, it is also evident from the literature that entrepreneurs' skill is also a key to business success (Dabić et al., 2020). Furthermore, an increase in the green environment of tourism also increases business success. Simultaneously, the entrepreneurs, particularly from Thailand, struggle with business success because of imperfection, weaknesses, and lack of strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill. Therefore, the current study's core objective is to explore the role of strategy management and entrepreneurs' skill on business success with the mediation role of tourism's green environment, especially in Thailand.

Contribution of a study is a critical point; hence, the current research with the complete explanation of the relationship between strategy management, entrepreneur's skill, green environment of tourism, and business success, has a theoretical and practical contribution. Theoretically, the current study examined the valuable relationship between strategy management and green environment of tourism, entrepreneurs' skill and green environment of tourism, strategy management and business success, entrepreneurs' skill and business success, and green environment of tourism and business success. The current study is a great contribution for the practitioners to increase business success, particularly in Thailand.

1. Literature Review

Several reasons are involved in the process of being successful in a business. An effective strategy, efficient processes, and marketable services or products are crucial for business success. A prior study describes that successful execution of plans, processes, and strategies guarantee business success. Lack of planning always leads to serious business failures; sometimes it even damages the whole structure of the business (Ferrari, 2020). It is evident that leadership also affects business success. In other words, plans and decisions have significant impacts on business success. Businesses with proper plans and accurate decisions always bring business to another extended level with more benefits and gains. Prior studies also show that regular interruptions damage the execution process of defined plans and strategies cause for business failures. Therefore, strategy management is an important part of a business that brings effective results regarding business success (Tohānean, Buzatu, Baba, & Georgescu, 2020). However, according to the current study besides, strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill is another effective factor that directly impacts business success. A previous study explores that entrepreneurs with the limited skill set or common skills always struggle to be prominent entrepreneurs. While the entrepreneurs with a unique skill always set successful to turns situations and things in their favor. Hence, entrepreneurs' skill has a significant role in business success (C. Li et al., 2020). While the green environment of tourism, which protects the economic, social, and environmental values of entrepreneurs, also positively impacts business success. The following Figure 1 shows the current study framework by exploring the relationship between key variables such as strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, green environment of tourism, and business success.

Figure 1. The study's theoretical framework shows the relationship between strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, green environment of tourism, and business performance.

1.1 Strategy Management and Green Environment of Tourism

The basic purpose of strategy management is to direct resources towards accomplishing specified targets with the successful implementation of plans. Strategy management involves analyzing the environment around, setting objectives, and ensuring plans' execution (Tran, Phan, Ha, & Hoang, 2020). A prior study explores that strategy management affects decision-making without going through strategy, resulting in losses instead of profit. Hence, strategy management is a very crucial part of the business unit. A green environment is an environment that is supportive in each condition, such as it supports economic, social, and custom growth of the region. A green tourism environment means tourism a tourism-friendly environment (Galeazzo, Ortiz-de-

Mandojana, & Delgado-Ceballos, 2020). A previous study shows that a green environment of tourism for a particular region protects the region economically.

Moreover, the acquisition of a green environment of tourism is necessarily required effective strategy management. Because strategy management helps define plans and directions (Choudhury, Paul, Rahman, Jia, & Shukla, 2020). Strategy management clears vision and objectives; hence, decision-making becomes more straightforward and persuasive. Furthermore, strategy management is compulsory for the efficient and effective execution of business plans. It is also clear from the previous literature that strategy management helps to reduce the risk of failure and innovate timely and early actions. Hence, with proper strategy management, the green environment of tourism becomes accessible (Kronenberg et al., 2020). Strategy management provides access to future directions and decisions that ultimately grow tourism's green environment. Therefore, better strategy management always results in a suitable green environment for tourism. According to the current study, strategy management is very beneficial for the green environment of tourism. Hence it is hypothesized that;

H1: Strategy management has a positive influence on the green environment of tourism.

1.2 Strategy Management and Business Success

Business success is a goal that involves a lot of effort and resources; some of them play their role with a direct relationship with business success while the other has an indirect relationship with the business. In a direct connection, the effecting factors have more importance as with slight change, and it also brings changes in the value of a business (Sadq, Khorsheed, Mohammed, & Othman, 2020). Therefore, factors especially related to the management unit, directly impacts business success. According to the current study, strategy management directly influences on business success. Results of a prior study describe that strategy management is responsible for all kind of business gains. No matter the volume of a business, it is always mandatory to go with a strategy (Harel, Schwartz, & Kaufmann, 2020). Because a business without strategy management is mostly unclear about its productivity, actual cost, and future decisions. Hence, strategy management is critical, especially from a business success point of view. Because strategy management enables a business to make the right and in-time decisions that provide the right people, product-market fit, financial knowledge, customer loyalty, action-oriented approach, effective processes, and an optimal business plan (Banik et al., 2020). With all the essential features that the only result of strategy management, business success becomes certain. Hence, according to the current study, businesses that opt proper and effective strategy management always gain profits according to their set goals.

Furthermore, such businesses are the achievers of competitive advantages among their competitors. The strategy management measures the edge of sales and willingness to work, analyze the market, choose the right team, build the right connections, and value customer service (Beverungen, Kundisch, & Wunderlich, 2020). Therefore, the influence of strategy management on business success is beneficial. Thus, it is capsulated that;

H2: Strategy management has a positive influence on business success.

1.3 Entrepreneurs' Skill and Green Environment of Tourism

Within definite energy, amount of time, or both to perform a task with fixed outcomes is called a skill. However, skills are divided into categories as per their nature and functionalities (Ahmed, Chandran, Klobas, Liñán, & Kokkalis, 2020). Generally, there are two major groups of skills; general skills and specific skills. According to the current study, entrepreneurs' skills are very important because they significantly influence business, entrepreneurs, and the environment. Previous research shows that entrepreneurs' skill differentiates them with their fellow entrepreneurs by advancing them with a better work-life balance, limiting independencies, wide accessibility, growing your confidence, contributing to world evolution development.

Moreover, entrepreneurs' skills positively impact personality development and improve the entrepreneurs as a person (Jena, 2020). A prior study explores that entrepreneurship is itself is a transversal skill which helps. At the same time, an entrepreneur passes through entrepreneurial programs conducted to enhance the potential to determine innovation and creativity, develop flexibility, proactivity, ability to manage, autonomy, pursuer getting results, and track a project. An environment that is altogether beneficial for every aspect of a specific business is called green environment (Omran, Zaid, & Dwekat, 2020). According to the current study green environment of tourism, particularly in Thailand, entrepreneurs' skill is directly influenced. Entrepreneurs' skill brings resilience, collaboration, and empathy in the environment that helps develop the green environment of tourism (Y. Li, Huang, & Song, 2020). Hence, the more entrepreneurs' skills, the greener environment of tourism developed. Thus, it is summarized that;

H3: Entrepreneurs' skill has a positive influence on the green environment of tourism.

1.4 Entrepreneurs' Skill and Business Success

There is a strong bond between skill and success. Without skills, success is almost impossible. According to a professor for division of natural and physical sciences, success without having skills is a matter of luck only, and luck is not a solution to any business problem (N. Z. F. Ismail & Mohamad, 2020). Skills are the tools which provides solutions to business problems and with these solutions entrepreneurs get business success. Entrepreneurs' skill makes them able to compete with their competitors that ultimately results in the accomplishment of competitive advantages as well (Olupayimo, 2020). A prior study explores that entrepreneurs

without the unique skillset always struggle and overall progress remains inferior. At the same time, the unique skill set of entrepreneurs assures prominent performance and progress that eventually lead them toward business success. It is also clear from the previous studies that entrepreneurs with common skills occasionally benefit while the entrepreneurs with the conspicuous skill set often gain business benefits. It is also noted that prominent skillset assists entrepreneurs with continual business gains (A. Ismail et al., 2019). Entrepreneurs who don't pay attention to learn new skills; instead, they rely on past experiences and believe habitual actions are hardly successful in their businesses. Because, in modern days, with an utmost increase in competition in almost every domain, entrepreneurs need to learn new experiences, knowledge, and skills which have the capability to assist them in completing with their competitor and cause for business success regularly (Rachapaettayakom, Wiriyaipinit, Cooharajanone, Tanthanongsakkun, & Charoenruk, 2020). According to the current study, entrepreneurs' skill has significant importance for business success. Hence, it is encapsulated that;

H4: Entrepreneurs' skill has a positive influence on business success.

1.5 Green Environment of Tourism and Business Success

A healthy environment with a tourism perspective that supports economic, social, and custom values is known as tourism's green environment (Joshi & Dhar, 2020). The acquisition of a proper environment has always been challenging for entrepreneurs. According to a previous study, the environment plays a significant role during the whole business process. An appropriate environment is good for the business process, but it also adds values to business growth (Zameer, Wang, Yasmeeen, & Mubarak, 2020). Therefore, entrepreneurs must develop an environment that has productive effects on the entire business process. A prior study shows that environmental distraction leads to a waste of time and resources, ultimately decreasing business progress. Therefore, the green environment of tourism supports business success (Shahzad, Qu, Zafar, Rehman, & Islam, 2020). That is why it is concluded that;

H5: Green environment of tourism has a positive influence on business success.

H6: Green environment of tourism mediates between the relationship of strategy management and business success.

H7: Green environment of tourism mediates between the relationship of entrepreneurs' skill and business performance.

2. Research Methodology

Out of three famous research methods among the researchers, quantitative research method, qualitative research method, and mixed-method, quantitative research method was adopted for the current study because the quantitative research method is just according to the nature of the current study. Moreover, the qualitative research method and mixed-method did not opt because the current study does not apply for both methods. Hence, it is better to go with the quantitative research method for the current study.

After a successful selection of quantitative research methods, area cluster sampling approach was preferred because the area under consideration for the current study was very wide. It is obvious that for a wide area, the area cluster sampling approach is very useful. Hence, area cluster sampling opted for the current study. Besides choosing the area cluster sampling approach, the current study's sample size was agreed upon 1000 because 1000 sample size is considered a perfect sample size.

In the next step, a questionnaire was composed. However, the questionnaire was composed of the following three different sections.

1. Personal information of the Respondents: In this section, respondents were responsible for answering questions asked about their personal information such as their experience, education, age, name, name of their concerned industry, if any, etc.
2. Questions related to critical variables of the current study: In the second section of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to answer questions related to key variables of the current study, such as questions contain these key variables strategy management, entrepreneurs' skill, green environment of tourism and business success.
3. 5-point Likert scale-based questions: In the third and the final section of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to choose from 5-point Likert scale-based questions. In this section, there were 20 questions based on the Likert scale.

As it is a survey-based study; hence, 1000 entrepreneurs from Thailand were selected as the respondents of the current study to collect the primary data. Hence, for the collection of primary data, initially, a list of entrepreneurs made, then it was decided that these respondents were contacted via their email service. Therefore, email addresses and other necessary contact information from the respondents were collected and saved in an organized manner. Then an email containing a copy of the questionnaire with a brief description of the objective of the current study was established. Then this email was sent to every respondent individually. After 15 days of successfully email sent to every respondent, 345 responses received from the respondents; hence, it was decided to send a reminder message through the email service to the rest of the respondents. Hence, 655 respondents were reminded; after 20 days of the reminder, there were 300 more responses. There were 645 total responses; however, out of 645, 23 responses were partially filled; hence, after removing these 23

responses, there were 622 responses used as primary data of the current study. Furthermore, with PLS's help, this primary data were analyzed to obtain the final results of the current study. All the scales and measures were opted from the previous studies.

3. Data Analysis

Both the outlier and the missing values present in data have severe effects for the study's final results. Hence, during the process of data screening, it was found that there is no missing value present in the collected data. Besides checking the primary data's missing value, the identification of outlier was ensured in the primary data. Moreover, missing values outlier identification is shown in Table 1. Besides this, Table 1 also indicates the normality of the data.

Table 1. Data Statistics

	No.	Missing	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Standard Deviation	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness
SM1	1	0	3.506	4	1	5	1.332	-0.847	-0.548
SM2	2	0	3.461	4	1	5	1.268	-0.954	-1.401
SM3	3	0	3.439	4	1	5	1.288	-1.964	-0.378
SM4	4	0	3.513	4	1	5	1.136	-0.623	-1.384
SM5	5	0	3.498	3	2	5	0.869	-0.667	0.006
SM6	6	0	3.413	3	2	5	0.843	-1.566	0.109
SM7	7	0	3.424	3	1	5	1.027	-0.207	-0.384
ES1	8	0	3.491	4	2	5	0.755	-0.342	-0.255
ES2	9	0	3.535	4	2	5	0.764	-0.3	-1.296
ES3	10	0	3.472	4	2	5	0.843	-1.595	-0.062
ES4	11	0	3.524	4	2	5	0.847	-0.585	-0.131
ES5	12	0	3.513	4	2	5	0.816	-0.494	-0.125
ES6	13	0	3.732	4	2	5	0.906	-0.682	-0.29
ES7	14	0	3.792	4	2	5	0.88	-1.659	-0.271
GE1	15	0	3.747	4	2	5	0.838	-0.53	-0.219
GE2	16	0	3.781	4	2	5	0.879	-0.632	-0.282
GE3	17	0	3.706	4	2	5	0.908	-0.741	-0.224
GE4	18	0	3.543	4	2	5	0.894	-0.749	-0.004
BS1	19	0	3.509	3	2	5	0.873	-0.683	0.056
BS2	20	0	3.468	4	1	5	1.047	-0.258	-0.404
BS3	21	0	3.539	4	2	5	0.855	-0.61	-0.104
BS4	22	0	3.61	4	2	5	0.933	-0.879	-0.06
BS5	23	0	3.643	4	2	5	0.916	-0.839	-0.078
BS6	24	0	3.799	4	2	5	0.931	-0.754	-0.34
BS7	25	0	3.844	4	2	5	0.907	-0.754	-0.317

After checking the normality of the data, then, validity and reliability were checked with PLS's help. In this part of the analysis, all the developed hypotheses were tested. The current study opted, Structural equation modeling (SEM). Generally, the two major steps are involved in PLS-SEM. The first step is the Measurement Model, while the second step is the Structural Model. At the same time, the reliability and validity of the data are shown by the measurement model. Hence, Figure 2 highlights the measurement model of the data. As it is highly recommended that the value of factor loadings should be above 0.4, the average variance extracted (AVE) should be higher than .5, and composite reliability (CR) should be more than 0.7. Hence, Table 2 clears that all the values are under the minimum threshold level. Moreover, in Table 3, discriminant validity is given.

Figure 2. Measurement Model

Table 2. Factor Loadings

	Business Success	Entrepreneurs Skill	Green Environment	Strategy Management
BS1	0.767			
BS2	0.71			
BS3	0.71			
BS4	0.701			
BS5	0.658			
BS6	0.522			
BS7	0.561			
ES1		0.418		
ES2		0.475		
ES3		0.724		
ES4		0.751		
ES5		0.671		
ES6		0.64		
ES7		0.658		
GE1			0.582	
GE2			0.623	
GE3			0.737	
GE4			0.747	
SM5				0.847
SM6				0.826
SM7				0.84

Table 3. Reliability and Convergent Validity

	Alpha	rho_A	CR	(AVE)
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Business Success	0.787	0.798	0.846	0.544
Entrepreneurs Skill	0.742	0.77	0.817	0.597
Green Environment	0.739	0.771	0.769	0.557
Strategy Management	0.788	0.789	0.876	0.702

Table 4. AVE Square Root

	Business Success	Entrepreneurs Skill	Green Environment	Strategy Management
Business Success	0.966			
Entrepreneurs Skill	0.828	0.83		
Green Environment	0.668	0.671	0.676	
Strategy Management	0.87	0.77	0.671	0.838

In the second step of PLS-SEM, hypotheses of the current study were tested using the structural model illustrated in Figure 4. Therefore, by using the structural model, seven hypotheses were tested in the current study. Out of the seven hypotheses, the five hypotheses were based on the direct effect of entrepreneurs' skill on business success, entrepreneur's skill on the green environment of tourism, green environment of tourism on business success, strategy management on business success, and strategy management on the green environment of tourism. Table 5 shows the direct effect of all these five hypotheses. Moreover, the structural model results, which is shown in Figure 3, are described in Table 5.

Figure 3. Structural Model

The t-value was based on tested these five hypotheses (Hameed, Nisar, & Wu, 2020). Hence, the hypotheses containing a t-value of more than 1.96 were only accepted, while the hypotheses containing a t-value below 1.96 were not accepted. Hence, it is clear in Table 5 that the relationship between entrepreneurs' skill and business success is significant with t-value 19.444 with $\beta = 0.645$. In this way, the relationship between entrepreneurs' skill and the green environment of tourism is also significant positive with a t-value of 3.854 with $\beta = .38$. The relationship between the green environment of tourism and business success has t-value below 1.96 with $\beta = -0.033$; hence, this hypothesis was not promoted. While the relationship between strategic management and business success has a meaningful t-value = 9.138 with the $\beta = 0.394$. In the fifth hypothesis, the relationship between strategy management and the green environment of tourism has a t-value = 3.946 with $\beta = 0.379$

Table 5. Direct Effect Results

	Original	Sample	Standard	T Statistics	P Values
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	Sample (O)	Mean (M)	Deviation (STDEV)	(O/STDEV)	
Entrepreneurs Skill -> Business Success	0.645	0.648	0.033	19.444	0
Entrepreneurs Skill -> Green Environment	0.38	0.376	0.099	3.854	0
Green Environment -> Business Success	-0.03	-0.033	0.032	0.912	0.362
Strategy Management -> Business Success	0.394	0.393	0.043	9.138	0
Strategy Management -> Green Environment	0.379	0.386	0.096	3.946	0

Furthermore, the two hypotheses (H6, H7) showed an indirect effect of tourism's green environment during the data analysis. The mediation effect of the green environment of tourism between the entrepreneur's skill and business success is significant, with t-value = 3.65 with $\beta = 0.01$. Simultaneously, the second mediation role of green environment of tourism between strategy management and business performance has a negative role with the significant t-value = 5.5 with $\beta = -0.011$. Table 6 shows the results which indicate that the green environment of tourism has positive effects on the mediation role between entrepreneurs' skill and business success. It is also clear that the mediation role of the green environment of tourism between strategy management and business success negatively affects the relationship.

Table 6. Indirect Effect Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Entrepreneurs Skill -> Green Environment -> Business Success	0.011	0.012	0.003	3.65	0
Strategy Management -> Green Environment -> Business Success	-0.011	-0.013	0.002	5.5	0

4. Discussion

According to the first hypothesis of the current study, strategy management has a positive influence on the green environment of tourism. There are many factors involved in the acquisition of a green environment suitable for business in every condition. Strategy management is one of the factors which directly impacts the green environment of tourism. A useful strategy is always helpful for developing an environment that supports business (Gulakov, Vanclay, & Arts, 2020). Hence, strategy management plays a vital role in the green environment of tourism, especially in Thailand. The second hypothesis of the current study describes that; strategy management has a positive influence on business success. Business success requires a lot of effort and resources. Business is an organized process in which workforce, energies, efforts, and resources are utilized to gain profits or benefits. However, management plays a vital role during the business process and has significant importance during the entire process (Lombardi, 2019). That's why strategy management has meaningful effects on business success. The third hypothesis of the current study determines that; Entrepreneurs' skill has a positive influence on the green environment of tourism. Entrepreneurs are very influential in any society. However, being a significant influence requires a lot of hard work and determination. As with hard work and determination, an entrepreneur is successful to learn unique skills. A unique set of skills is an attribute, which makes an entrepreneur distinguished from common entrepreneurs (Lackeus, 2020). Hence, entrepreneurs' skill matters a lot for the green environment of tourism. According to the fourth hypothesis of the current study, entrepreneurs' skill has a positive influence on business success. With a lot of energies, investment, and resources, business success requires the most is entrepreneurs' skill. As skill is an ability that determines the capability of an entrepreneur, either he/she can do business in an effective way or remain ineffective during the business process. Quality of skill matters a lot during the whole business process; skill with a great quality ensures business success (Aydiner, Tatoglu, Bayraktar, & Zaim, 2019). While common skills, past practices, and custom approaches don't bring success in a regular way. Therefore, entrepreneurs' skill has numerous impacts on business success. The fifth hypothesis of the current study explores that; green environment of tourism has a positive influence on business success. An environment plays an essential role in starting and growing an activity. According to the results of a prior study, a suitable environment is always helpful for business. Without a proper environment, there is always distraction from each direction which ultimately reduces progress. Hence, it becomes more essential to produce an environment which supports a business process instead of being a reason for distraction. An environment that is altogether supportive of a business is known as a green environment (Tian, Zhang, & Li, 2020). According to the current study, the green environment of tourism plays a vital role in business success. The last two hypotheses of the current study describe that; green environment of tourism mediates between the relationship of strategy management and business success. And the green environment of tourism mediates between the relationship of entrepreneurs' skill and business performance.

5. Conclusion

The results of the current study explore that strategy management plays a vital role in the acquisition of a green environment of tourism and business success, particularly in Thailand. Moreover, strategy management enables an entrepreneur to analyze the entire business process that helps in decision making and plans development. Furthermore, entrepreneurs' skill is a fundamental attribute that directly influences both the green environment of tourism and business success. According to the current study, entrepreneurs with quality skillset always find acclaimed status in business society, while with a common skill set, it is always hard to compete with the market and the competitor. Hence, entrepreneurs' skill also has numerous influences on the acquisition of a green environment of tourism and business success. A survey-based on 622 entrepreneurs from Thailand was conducted to obtain primary data for the current study; moreover, to finalize its results PLS was used for data analysis purposes. The current study explores that strategy management directly influences the green environment of tourism and business success. While entrepreneurs' skill also has a direct relationship with the green environment of tourism and business success. Besides having a direct impact on business success, the green environment of tourism also mediates between the relationship of strategy management and business success and entrepreneurs' skill and business success. Practically, the current study is an excellent contribution for the entrepreneurs and the practitioners to bring regulation in their business success.

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